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Acropora retusa coral species critical habitat for use in ESA/FIFRA consultations

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Data Set (DS) | NMFS Office Of Protected Resources (OPR)

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:72761 | Updated: September 17, 2025 | Published / External

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NMFS Office Of Protected Resources, 2026: Acropora retusa coral species critical habitat for use in ESA/FIFRA consultations, <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/inport/item/72761>.

Item Identification

Title: Acropora retusa coral species critical habitat for use in ESA/FIFRA consultations

Status: Completed

Publication Date: 2024-07-01

Abstract: These data represent critical habitat designated (July 15, 2025) under the Endangered Species Act for the coral *Acropora retusa* at 5 island units in American Samoa (Tutuila, Ofu & Olosega, Ta'u, Rose Atoll, and Swains). Please refer to the Code of Federal Regulations and the supporting information report for more details and consider the regulatory language when using these spatial data. <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/action/critical-habitat-designations-threatened-corals-us-waters-pacific-islands> Specific areas of critical habitat for the Indo-Pacific coral species *Acropora retusa* include marine area around 5 island units in American Samoa (Tutuila, Ofu & Olosega, Ta'u, Rose Atoll, and Swains) with suitable hard-bottom habitat within the depth range 0-20 m, as described below. Specific areas of critical habitat were delineated in four steps: (1) General information was used to delineate soft vs.

hard substrates, leaving only hard substrate areas; (2) for the hard substrate areas identified in Step 1, specific substrate information was used to delineate unsuitable vs. suitable hard substrates, leaving only the latter; (3) for the suitable hard substrate areas identified in Step 2, we used water quality information to further delineate suitable vs. unsuitable areas; and (4) from the suitable areas identified in Steps 1–3, we removed any overlapping artificial substrates and managed areas. The four steps were implemented for each of the 20 units as follows: For Step 1, we used comprehensive hard-soft substrate maps developed by PIFSC (PIFSC 2021) to delineate soft vs. hard substrates, leaving only hard substrate areas within the combined depth ranges of all listed species in each unit for 18 of the 20 units. For Wake Atoll, we used the substrate map from PIBHMC (2021). For French Frigate Shoals, we used the geomorphological structure component of the maps developed by NCCOS (2003). For Step 2, we started with the hard substrate areas identified in Step 1, then distinguished unsuitable vs. suitable hard substrates. Many hard substrates are unsuitable because: (1) highly-fluctuating physical conditions cause extreme changes in water quality (e.g., shallow pavement and rubble on reef flats, rock/boulder in the intertidal zone); (2) water motion continuously mobilizes sediment (e.g., pavement with sand channels) or unstable substrate (e.g., rubble); or (3) flat, low-relief areas provide poor settlement and growth habitat (e.g., pavement). Removal of these areas left suitable hard substrates, including spur-and-groove, individual patch reef, aggregate reef, aggregated patch reef, scattered coral/rock, and subtidal rock/boulder. For this step, primary information sources were Brainard et al. (2008, 2012, 2019), Kendall and Poti (2011), NCCOS (2003, 2005, 2010), PIBHMC (2021), PIFSC (2021), the detailed public comment letters from the Territories (AS DMWR 2021, CNMI DLNR 2021, CNMI Governor 2024, Guam DOAG 2021), and the American Samoa, Guam, CNMI, PRIA, and NWHI chapters in Waddell and Clarke (2008). Additional sources for individual units are cited in the unit sections below. For Step 3, starting with the suitable hard substrate areas identified in Step 2, we used water quality information to further delineate suitable vs. unsuitable areas. Some of the areas identified in Step 2 are chronically subject to pollution such as excessive nutrients, excessive sediment, contaminants, or other water quality problems, making them unsuitable. Generally, such areas occur in enclosed lagoons and inner harbors where there is high runoff and limited water circulation. Outside of such areas, point and non-point sources of pollution generally do not overlap with suitable hard substrates because wastewater outfalls are located on soft substrates beyond the reef slopes, and stormwater and freshwater discharge occurs primarily on soft substrates (sand or mud) or unsuitable hard substrates (pavement or rubble) along or near shorelines. For this step, primary information sources were Brainard et al. (2008, 2012, 2019), EPA (2021a-f), the detailed public comment letters from the Territories (AS DMWR 2021, 2024, CNMI DLNR 2021, CNMI Governor 2024, Guam DOAG 2021, 2024), Territory water quality assessments (AS EPA 2020, CNMI BECQ 2018, 2020), and sources for individual units cited in the unit sections below. For Step 4, from the suitable areas identified via the above three steps, we removed any artificial substrates and managed areas, because they do not provide the essential feature, as explained in section 3.2.3 above. This only applies to existing artificial substrates and managed areas, not proposed or planned artificial substrates and managed areas. For more details and complete citations see the

Critical Habitat Information Report: <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/s3/2025-07/final-info-report-piro-coral-pir-2025.pdf> Links to the full text of the final rule in the Federal Register and other supporting materials can be found here: <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/action/critical-habitat-designations-threatened-corals-us-waters-pacific-islands>

Purpose:

This spatial data file was modified from NMFS’s “agency-official” species critical habitat data to aid in the ESA/FIFRA section 7 pesticide consultation process. For example, existing data were adapted to incorporate associated watersheds where applicable, based on the USGS Watershed Boundary Dataset HUC-12 data (<https://www.usgs.gov/national-hydrography/watershed-boundary-dataset>). The modifications to the NMFS critical habitat spatial data make the data more compatible for future analyses with EPA’s Use Data Layers (UDLs). The following “Description” is from the original, “agency-official” data that was used to make this HUC-based map. Most of the metadata record for this species matches the “agency-official” record; however, NMFS added a new “Citation”, “File Identifier”, “Credits”, “Point of Contact”, and “Lineage Process Step” that are unique to this HUC-based critical habitat data.

Keywords

Theme Keywords

Thesaurus	Keyword
ISO 19115 Topic Category	biota
ISO 19115 Topic Category	boundaries
ISO 19115 Topic Category	oceans

Physical Location

City: Honolulu

State/Province: HI

Data Set Information

Data Set Scope Code: Data Set

Maintenance Frequency: As Needed

Data Presentation Form: Map (digital)

Data Set Credit: CREDIT: NOAA Fisheries. 2025. Species Critical Habitats for ESA/FIFRA Consultations Geodatabase. Silver Spring, MD: National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), Office of Protected Resources (OPR). This HUC-based critical habitat dataset for ESA/FIFRA section 7 pesticide consultations is courtesy of National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) Office of Protected Resources (OPR): Karrin Goodman. The original data is courtesy of National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), Pacific Islands Regional Office. ORIGINATORS: National Marine Fisheries Service, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration; NMFS Office of Protected Resources;

Support Roles

Data Steward		CC ID: 1428479
Date Effective From:	2020-10-13	
Date Effective To:		
Contact (Person):	Regional Office, Pacific Islands	
Email Address:	piro.info@noaa.gov	

Data Steward		CC ID: 1428480
Date Effective From:	2020-10-13	
Date Effective To:		

Contact (Person): Goodman, Karrin

Email Address: karrin.goodman@noaa.gov

Phone: (301) 427-8435

Metadata Contact

CC ID: 1428483

Date Effective From: 2020-10-13

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Regional Office, Pacific Islands

Email Address: piro.info@noaa.gov

Metadata Contact

CC ID: 1428484

Date Effective From: 2020-10-13

Date Effective To:

Contact (Person): Goodman, Karrin

Email Address: karrin.goodman@noaa.gov

Phone: (301) 427-8435

Point of Contact

CC ID: 1428481

Date Effective From: 2020-10-13

Date Effective To:

Contact Regional Office, Pacific Islands

Person):

Email Address: piro.info@noaa.gov

Point of Contact

CC ID: 1428482

Date Effective 2020-10-13
From:

Date Effective
To:

Contact Goodman, Karrin
(Person):

Email Address: karrin.goodman@noaa.gov

Phone: (301) 427-8435

Extents

Currentness Publication Date
Reference:

Extent Group 1

Extent specific marine areas within nearshore waters of 5 island units in American
Description: Samoa (Tutuila, Ofu & Olosega, Ta'u, Rose Atoll, and Swains).

Extent Group 1 / Geographic Area 1

CC ID: 1428491

W° Bound: -171.14258
7

E° Bound: -168.08694
8

N° Bound: -10.995661

S° Bound: -14.610193

Extent Group 1 / Time Frame 1

CC ID: 1428490

Time Frame Type: Discrete

Start: 2025-07-15 00:00:00+0000

Spatial Information

Reference Systems

Reference System 1

CC ID: 1428487

Coordinate Reference System

CRS Type: Geographic 2D

EPSG Code: EPSG:4269

EPSG Name: NAD83

▼ [See Full Coordinate Reference System Information](#)

Access Information

Security Class: Unclassified

Data Use Constraints: These spatial data are not the official legal definitions of critical habitat. Proposed rules, final rules, and the Code of Federal Regulations (50 CFR 226) are the official sources of critical habitat. The accuracy of these datasets are dependent upon the accuracy and resolution of the datasets (e.g. shoreline, hydrography, bathymetry, shared administrative boundaries) used in the creation process.*** Attribution *** Whenever NMFS material is reproduced and

re-disseminated, we request that users attribute the material appropriately. Pursuant to 17 U.S.C. 403, parties who produce copyrighted works consisting predominantly of material created by the Federal Government are encouraged to provide notice that such work(s) identifying the U.S. Government material incorporated and stating that such material is not subject to copyright protection. Please cite the datasets as follows, with the appropriate information substituted for all text in {CURLY BRACKETS}: NOAA Fisheries Service. National Endangered Species Act Critical Habitat Geodatabase. Silver Spring, MD: National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), Office of Protected Resources (OPR) {GEODATABASE PUBLICATION DATE}. {ADD URL}*** No Warranty*** The user assumes the entire risk related to its use of these data. NOAA is providing these data "as is," and &organization& disclaims any and all warranties, whether express or implied, including (without limitation) any implied warranties of merchantability or fitness for a particular purpose. No warranty expressed or implied is made regarding the accuracy or utility of the data on any other system or for general or scientific purposes, nor shall the act of distribution constitute any such warranty. It is strongly recommended that careful attention be paid to the contents of the metadata file associated with these data to evaluate dataset limitations, restrictions or intended use. In no event will &organization& be liable to you or to any third party for any direct, indirect, incidental, consequential, special or exemplary damages or lost profit resulting from any use or misuse of this data.*** Proper Usage *** The information on government servers are in the public domain, unless specifically annotated otherwise, and may be used freely by the public. Before using information obtained from this server, special attention should be given to the date and time of the data and products being displayed. This information shall not be modified in content and then presented as official government material. These datasets were created to generally represent our best professional judgment of the ranges and designated or proposed critical habitat of listed species based on the best available information at the time of publication, including: geographic factors, time of year, and the biology of each species. The dataset should not be used to infer information regarding the existence or details of other marine features or resources, including, but not limited to, navigable waters, coastlines, bathymetry, submerged features, or man-made structures. Users assume responsibility for determining the appropriate use of this dataset.

Technical Environment

Description: Microsoft Windows 10 Version 10.0 (Build 26100) ; Esri ArcGIS 13.1.3.41833

Lineage

Lineage Statement: This spatial data file was modified from NMFS's "agency-official" species critical habitat data to aid in the ESA/FIFRA section 7 pesticide consultation process. For example, existing data were adapted to incorporate associated watersheds

where applicable, based on the USGS Watershed Boundary Dataset HUC-12 data (<https://www.usgs.gov/national-hydrography/watershed-boundary-dataset>). The modifications to the NMFS critical habitat spatial data make the data more compatible for future analyses with EPA's Use Data Layers (UDLs).

The following statement is from the original "agency-official" metadata:

Coral critical habitat for *A. retusa* includes specific areas within certain depth ranges around the following five islands in American Samoa, as described below:

1. Tutuila and Offshore Banks (American Samoa): specific areas described in Section 3.4.1 within a depth range of 0 – 20 m.
2. Ofu-Olosega (American Samoa): specific areas described in Section 3.4.2 within a depth range of 0 –20 m.
3. Ta'u (American Samoa): specific areas described in Section 3.4.3 within a depth range of 0 – 20 m.
4. Rose Atoll(American Samoa): specific areas described in Section 3.4.4 within a depth range of 0 –20 m.
5. Swains (American Samoa): specific areas described in Section 3.4.5 within a depth range of 0 –20 m.

Section numbers above refer to sections of the Final Information Report which can be found under "Supporting Materials" on the following webpage URL. See report for more details. <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/action/critical-habitat-designations-threatened-corals-us-waters-pacific-islands>

Bathymetric data sources used include:

- NOAA NGS 2022 Topobathy LiDAR for the islands of Ofu-Olosega, Ta'u, Rose Atoll, and Swains;
- NOAA NCEI CUDEM for Tutuila (accessed 2024-05-21);

LiDAR datasets were downloaded as 1 m DEMs via NOAA Digital Coast's Data Access Viewer, then aggregated to 10 m resolution, gap-filled with the 'elevation void fill' raster function in ArcGIS Pro for small gaps (if needed) and/or mosaicked with NOAA CUDEM data as needed for larger holes.

Relevant depth range polygons were generated from the final bathymetry grids and NOAA CUSP shorelines (except at Rose, where the NCCOS habitat map shoreline was more accurate). These polygons were then clipped to areas of suitable hard substrate from NOAA NCCOS benthic habitat maps, and then ineligible areas, maintained navigation channels, and areas with poor water quality were erased.

Resulting polygons smaller than 100 m² (the equivalent of a solitary 10 x 10 m pixel) were removed.

Process Steps

Process Step 1

CC ID: 1428485

Description: As described above, this species’ HUC-based critical habitat dataset was modified from the polygon-based species “agency-official” NMFS critical habitat data. This HUC-based critical habitat file represents the HUC-12 watersheds (USGS Watershed Boundary Dataset; <https://www.usgs.gov/national-hydrography/watershed-boundary-dataset>) that intersect with the “agency-official” critical habitat polygon-based data. The data were reviewed and revised to add any additional HUC-12 watersheds that were determined to have hydrologic connectivity to the critical habitat.

Process Date/Time: 2023-12-15 00:00:00

Process Contact: NMFS Office Of Protected Resources (OPR)

Phone (Voice): 301-713-2332

Child Items

Rubric scores updated every 15m

Type

Title

Entity

[CoralAcroporaRetusa_10340_CH](#)

Catalog Details

Catalog Item ID: 72761

GUID: gov.noaa.nmfs.inport:72761

Metadata Record Created By: Karrin N Goodman

Metadata Record Created: 2024-06-03 22:06+0000

Metadata Record Last: Karrin N Goodman

Modified By:

Metadata 2025-09-17 17:16+0000

Record Last Modified:

Metadata 2025-09-17

Record Published:

Owner Org: OPR

Metadata Publication Status: Published Externally

Do Not Publish?: N

Metadata Review Frequency: 1 Year

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Release 6.0.5

Build FINAL (2025-12-02 18:25 UTC)

